

DIGITALIZATION AND THE DIGITAL ECONOMY AND THE CHANGES THEY INTRODUCE INTO OUR LIVES

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6582057>

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Abstract: The urgency of the problems of the formation of the digital economy is due to both the growth of the scale of social communications through social networks and the effectiveness of digital platforms that increase the speed and diversity of exchanges (through the use of technologies based on the use of features of discreteness, programmability and algorithmicity of production processes), which in general opens up fundamentally new and broader opportunities for increasing the efficiency of mass production, development economy and society. The term "digital economy" is widely used both in theory and in practice, but there is no consensus on its interpretation. According to the well-known statements formulated by Stan Kaplan in his methods of risk analysis, 50% of the problems in the world arise from situations when the same words are used to denote different concepts, and the same number appears because the same concepts are interpreted in different words. This conclusion is also characteristic of the digital economy, where the term "digital economy" is often widely used by journalists and specialists in relation to various areas of digitalization in order to attract attention to the digital topic, as a result of which the pace of semantic changes is constantly increasing and, as a result, there is a risk of blurring the boundaries of a new sphere of knowledge, loss of its identity and investment attractiveness.

It is advisable to consider the process of digitalization in a broad and narrow sense. The first is understood as multidimensional organizational and technological processes of mass application of new digital technologies in production and management in order to reduce costs and increase the speed of business processes. In the second, narrower, technical plan, it means the transition from an analog form of transmission, processing and presentation of data (information) to a digital one, carried out through the use of appropriate technologies and platforms. According to economic logic, the advantages of digitalization become obvious, which are determined by the following efficiency factors:

acceleration of the use of new market opportunities by enterprises due to direct digital signals from the external environment;

improving the quality of customer service by simplifying and reducing the cost of data collection to personalize their requests and maintain constant communication with them;

expanding the ability to optimize business processes (by eliminating delays as much as possible), as well as their simplification and acceleration due to digital devices;

increasing the target audience and geographical coverage of the enterprise through the use of all forms of digital channels and their points of contact.

These factors are of tactical importance and are more typical for an enterprise switching to the use of digital technologies in the production and marketing of products. To form a national strategy in the field of digitalization and the digital economy, it is important to take into account that the relevance of digitalization is due to the growing scale of social communications carried out through networks and digital platforms that increase the speed and diversity of exchanges and open up fundamentally wider opportunities for the development of the economy and society. Suppliers and consumers are increasingly interacting with each other without intermediaries, and price factors linking supply and demand are being replaced by new mechanisms of cooperation, which, in turn, expands markets in terms of the composition of participants and the variety of products, leads to accelerated application of technical and organizational innovations in enterprises that are becoming more flexible and maneuverable.

At the same time, a distributed model of coordination of interconnections between producers and consumers through network nodes (hybrid network order) is being formed, which allows systems of all levels to increase their adaptability to changes in the external environment. The advantages of horizontal network interactions over hierarchical ones are the basis for new economic growth, which always depends on the speed and variety of exchanges. According to the Nobel laureate Fr. The Williamson post-industrial economy builds itself in the form of a set of horizontal (non-hierarchical) network partnerships, which are much more flexible in their configuration than rigid vertical hierarchies, and at the same time more integrated than flexible, but atomistic markets. That is, the creation by the state of opportunities for the unification and skillful use of information (knowledge) in the course of communications through networks

and platforms is an essential condition for innovation and growth of the post-industrial economy. The consequence of digitalization is a more complete application of feedback mechanisms in management, since they allow us to determine measures to increase the sustainability and efficiency of economic activity in accordance with the plans. Based on these theoretical provisions, it can be assumed that digitalization is not a goal, but a means, and the digital economy cannot be considered separately from the rest of the economy and should be interpreted as a segment of activity when the materialization of added value in the production of goods and services is carried out using digital technologies, especially for industries that are Internet-dependent. At the same time, it makes sense and value if digital technologies and infrastructure promote cooperation in all spheres of the economy and levels of management. At the same time, a comfortable environment is being formed for the emergence, cultivation and implementation of various startups.

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